

Odo Magdunensis and the *Macer floridus*

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Abstract

Odo Magdunensis' *De viribus herbarum* (transmitted as the *Macer floridus*) is a Latin hexameter didactic poem on medicinal plants that became a standard point of reference for medieval materia medica. The work condenses late antique authorities, especially Dioscorides, Pliny and Galen, and in expanded form incorporates graded pharmacology lifted from Constantinus Africanus (*Liber graduum*). Its transmission is marked by openness to rearrangement and accretion, including the *Spuria Macri* and the emergence of the German prose *Macer* (c. 1220), which reflects shifting audiences and functions. Persistent problems include the instability of author attributions under the name "Macer" and recurrent uncertainties of drug identification, while the reception can be traced into early modern herbals and, in selected cases, into later phytotherapeutic discourse.

This brief outlines authorship, dating, transmission, translations, and current research trends, linking the philological work of Johannes G. Mayer and Konrad Goehl (2013) [MG], Bernhard Schnell and William Crossgrove (2003) [SC], and Ulrike Jansen (2013) [J] with the current significance of the plants discussed.

Keywords: Odo of Meung; Odo Magdunensis; *Macer floridus*; *De viribus herbarum*; German *Macer*; medieval herbal; didactic poetry; Salerno; Constantinus Africanus; *Liber graduum*; vernacular translations; textual transmission; *Spuria Macri*; reception history

Author and author-construct

The author of *De viribus herbarum* is identified with Odo Magdunensis (Odo of Meung), but biographical indications remain sparse. On the basis of linguistic profile and education, he was more likely a magister than a practising physician [SC 27].

In transmission, the text circulates under the author name "Macer". Explicit ascriptions such as "Odonis magdunensis opusculum de naturis herbarum" (Dresden, Dc 160, late 12th century) or "auctore Odone dicto macro florigio" (Douai 217, 13th century) are rare. The identification with the ancient Aemilius Macer (d. 16 BC) is less a reliable author attribution than a signal of *auctoritas*. The false attribution to Aemilius Macer is explained by medieval canon formation, in which ancient names served as guarantors of credibility. Ovid (Trist. IV, 10, 43-44) and Isidore (Etym. XII, 7, 9) mention a Macer as author of works on birds, snakes, and herbs.

The byname "floridus" is first attested in the 13th century (Douai 217) and was canonised through incunable printing. It may have arisen through misreading from "philosophus" [MG]. The competition with attributions such as "Odo Muremundensis" (Morimond) requires stemmatic clarification [SC 27, 29].

Dating

The earliest mention of the *Macer* occurs around 1100 in Sigebert of Gembloux (*De scriptoribus ecclesiasticis*). Accordingly, the final redaction (77 chapters) is dated before 1112. For the shorter original version (ca. 50–60 chapters) a window within the eleventh century is assumed; the older attribution to the ancient Aemilius Macer has been rejected as irrelevant [Crossgrove 1994; Flood 1976; SC 24–26].

In the first half of the twelfth century, the English historian Henry of Huntingdon (ca. 1088–1157) used the didactic poem as the principal source for his *Anglicanus ortus* (“English Garden”), a Latin hexameter poem on England’s native medicinal plants. Henry, Archdeacon of Huntingdon and author of the *Historia Anglorum*, adopted Odo’s verse form and structural scheme, yet adapted it to British flora. The *Anglicanus ortus* attests the early diffusion of the *Macer* beyond the French-speaking sphere and its exemplary function for emerging vernacular herbal literature. The Gradus system is a central marker for dating. Because parts of the text draw on Constantinus Africanus’ *Liber graduum*, composition before the late 11th century is unlikely [SC 24]. Crossgrove identified a “proto-*Macer*” in 1994, without the Constantinian additions (chaps. 67–77). Whether Odo himself was responsible for the expansion or a later redactor remains open [SC 26]. The layering of the expansions and their relation to manuscript variability are not definitively clarified. A more precise dating of the original version remains a desideratum [SC 23–24, 60].

Text and sources

De viribus herbarum is a pharmakographic didactic poem in hexameters, not a garden or nature poem in the manner of Walafrid Strabo’s *Hortulus*, although Odo partially adopts and discusses Walafrid’s plant list (thus, for example, he criticises Walafrid’s claim that lovage harms the eyes). In the editorial tradition, the text often appears with 2269 verses and 77 plant chapters (Choulant 1832). The chapter sequence is variable in manuscript transmission; stability lies more on the level of individual plant monographs than on the level of a fixed overall arrangement [SC 22–23].

The main sources are Pliny, Dioscorides, and Galen; Salernitan adaptations supplement the material in the expanded version. Typical building blocks of the herbal monograph include names and synonyms; humoral qualities (warm, cold, moist, dry); actions and indications according to the scheme *a capite ad calcem*; preparations and modes of application. Odo integrates the Salernitan Gradus doctrine (intensity levels 1–4) [SC 4–5, MG].

The style is matter-of-fact and oriented toward the transmission of knowledge. Hexameter serves as a mnemonic medium; models include Roman didactic poetry such as Virgil’s *Georgica*. Unlike the *Hortulus* with its lyrical ambitions, the *Macer* pursues not a poetic but a didactic agenda [MG].

A systematic investigation of the Salernitan additions in the expanded version is still lacking. The editorial infrastructure for the Latin tradition remains a desideratum: Choulant’s edition (1832) is historically important, but no longer sufficient [SC; Crossgrove 1994].

Genre and openness to compilation

Medieval herbals are structurally open. Insertions, omissions, and rearrangements are possible, and compilation is the normal mode of transmission. *Materia medica* was traditionally divided into herbals (plants), bestiaries (animal products), and lapidaries (minerals). The *Macer* concentrates on the plant realm, but in expanded versions also integrates mineral and animal substances [SC 4–5].

The *Macer* corpus is a dynamic formation. The expansions indicate connectivity and functional change. In composite manuscripts, the *Macer* merges with prose texts (e.g. the Bartholomaeus tract); recipients used the work as a reference for self-medication [J 2, 10; MG].

A systematic comparison between the Latin didactic poem and subordinate compilations with respect to routes of transmission and the layering of added substances in the transition from manuscript to print remains to be undertaken [SC 23–24; J 6, 12].

Spuria Macri

Under the label *Spuria Macri* are twenty chapters (Aaron to Alumen) that appear as an appendix to the *Macer* in the early print tradition (Cornarius 1540, Ranzovius 1590). They extend the botanical frame by animal and mineral substances (Fel, Fimus, Cornu cervi, Sulphur vivum, Alumen) [J 1, 9–10].

In manuscript transmission, individual *Spuria* chapters circulate alphabetically. A central witness is Fulda, Hs. C 9 (fourteenth century), which transmits fourteen of the twenty chapters in altered form [J 2, 6].

The *Spuria* complex is the product of movements in transmission, not the work of an identifiable author. As a source horizon, an eleventh-century Dioscorides tradition is assumed, together with Pliny, Isidore, and, indirectly, Gargilius Martialis [J 1–2, 12]. The author was presumably a student of Odo, who continued his mnemonic approach [J 71]. The *Spuria* have an independent genesis and require separate textual criticism [J].

The distribution of the *Spuria* in manuscript transmission, the interference of layers, and the relation of alphabetical processing to the printed versions require more precise analysis [J 6, 12].

The German *Macer*

The emergence of the German *Macer* (vulgate version) is placed around 1220 in the Thuringian–Upper Saxon region, possibly in the milieu of Duke Henry in Brunswick. The German text is a translation of an expanded Latin exemplar that extended beyond the Choulant text and included portions from the *Liber graduum* [SC 59–60].

The German *Macer* is the first German prose version and is considered the earliest significant German-language herbal, a key text of vernacular medical erudition. A rhymed rendering followed only later. The choice of prose marks a paradigmatic shift: away from mnemonic verse toward readable technical prose [MG].

The shift from hexameter to prose went along with interventions: omissions (learned exempla, myths, etymologies); deletion of recipes concerning sexuality; securing comprehension by glossing (*menstruum* as “vrowensuche”, *cancer* as “bose geswer”). The German *Macer* is technical prose for a lay user group (women’s convents, courts) [SC 76–82].

The anonymous “Speyer herbal” (mid-fifteenth century) is a witness to compilation practice in late medieval herbal literature: it combines material from the Latin *Macer*, the German *Macer*, Hildegard’s *Physica*, and the *Circa instans*. Johann Wonnecke of Kaub adopted this compilation for his *Gart der Gesundheit* (1485) [Fehring 1994; Lichtenwagner 2019].

Whether the additional concluding chapters were already part of the Latin exemplar or derive from the Bartholomaeus milieu is unclear. The stemmatic placement of the vulgate version remains outstanding [SC 60].

Further vernacular translations

Alongside the German *Macer*, translations and reworkings survive in numerous European vernaculars: Middle English, Old French, Spanish, Danish, Italian. In the late Middle Ages the *Macer* has been attested in roughly every second noteworthy library [MG; SC 205–219].

The Middle English tradition includes the *Lelamour Herbal* (London, British Library, MS Sloane 5), edited in 2018 by David Moreno Olalla. Work on individual branches of the translation tradition is expanding [Moreno Olalla 2018].

The vernacular translations attest the *Macer*’s pan-European reach. Unlike the *Hortulus* or Hildegard’s *Physica*, which remained regionally limited, the *Macer* achieved a Europe-wide reception.

Systematic comparative studies of the vernacular versions (text selection, strategies of adaptation, audience) remain a desideratum.

Manuscript transmission

131 witnesses of the German *Macer* have been recorded; after excluding small fragments, 107 manuscripts remain that transmit the text complete, in compilations, or in excerpts. In the fifteenth century the audience shifts from Latin-literate readers to vernacular-reading medical laypersons [SC 205–219].

Transmission clusters are the norm; the *Macer* often appears with the Bartholomaeus tract or Ortolf’s medical book. For his *Gart der Gesundheit* (1485), Johann Wonnecke of Kaub relied on the Speyer herbal and thus indirectly adopted *Macer* material, which he, however, disguised as quotations from ancient authorities. Via Lonitzer and Tabernaemontanus, this knowledge entered Zedler’s *Universallexikon* [MG, SC 83].

The correlation of editorial interventions with specific transmission clusters and the change of audience requires investigation [SC 76–82, 219].

Print transmission

The first printed edition of the Latin *Macer* appeared on 9 May 1477 in Naples, produced by Arnold of Brussels. Around 1500 an illustrated branch with woodcuts emerged: Paris 1506 and 1511, an undated Paris edition; further illustrated prints followed into the sixteenth century (Kraków 1537; Basel 1559/1581), in part with the Gueroaldus commentary [Choulant 1832; SC 83–84].

The transition to incunable printing (*Herbarius Moguntinus* 1484, *Hortus sanitatis* 1491) is the final stage of the medieval *Macer* tradition before early modern botany pursued its own paths.

In the nineteenth century, Choulant produced an edition (1832) that is still used today, although it is outdated. The authoritative

edition of the German *Macer* with an extensive introduction is that of Schnell & Crossgrove (2003); in an appendix they print the Latin *Macer floridus De viribus herbarum* (excluding the *Spuria* printed by Choulant; only the pieces relevant to the German text are included) [SC].

A modern critical edition of the Latin text that brings together both main versions and the appendix on a broad manuscript basis remains a desideratum [SC; Crossgrove 1994].

Identification of drugs

Most plants of the 77 chapters of the Latin version can today be delimited relatively narrowly, since the medieval names have often entered modern botanical nomenclature. In some cases, however, identification remains disputed [Niedenthal 2020].

Chapter 50 (*Barrocum*). Since the nineteenth century, lemon balm has been suggested, alternatively Immenblatt, white dead-nettle, or meadowsweet. The Greek–Latin name *melissophyllum* points to the first two; the woodcut in early prints leaves all options open.

Chapter 64 (*Lolium/Nigella*). Black cumin is to be excluded. Possible candidates are darnel (*Lolium temulentum*) or corncockle (*Agrostemma githago*). The German vulgate version gives “Raten”; the same uncertainty is found in Hildegard and in the *Gart der Gesundheit*.

Chapter 75 (*Spica*). Indian nard (*Nardostachys grandiflora*) and Celtic valerian (*Valeriana celtica*) are named. Since nard was scarcely available in the Middle Ages, (spikenard-)lavender must be considered as a substitute.

The stylised woodcuts of the early prints are of limited use for identification. More informative is comparison between the Latin version and the German vulgate version, as well as comparison with other herbals.

Continuity into modern phytotherapy

In 1872 Josef Haupt wrote: “Once the *Macer* is printed, even dull eyes will understand that a mass not only of our household remedies has reached the people by way of learned transmission.” Many applications listed in Hager’s encyclopedia as “popular” (mugwort, garlic, nettle) go back to Odo’s hexameters.

For a substantial part of the plants, positive monographs exist from Commission E, ESCOP, or HMPC, including wormwood, nettle, garlic, ribwort plantain, marshmallow, chamomile, fennel, rose, sage, lovage, horehound, wild mallow, ginger, clove, cinnamon, and aloe.

For some spice plants (dill, coriander, watercress, white mustard, galangal) only Commission E monographs exist. In the case of marjoram, a negative Commission E assessment was later replaced by a positive HMPC monograph. For frankincense only an ESCOP monograph exists (*Boswellia serrata*); Odo probably meant *B. sacra*.

Among the drugs removed from the pharmacopoeial stock since DAB/EB6 are, inter alia, mugwort, rue, savin, summer savory, masterwort, black mustard, sweet violet, German iris, elecampane, hyssop, hazelwort, peony, Christmas rose, vervain, pepper, pellitory, and zedoary, the plants of 18 *Macer* chapters.

In the case of celandine and henbane, Commission E monographs are obsolete because of toxicological concerns; HMPC discontinued the procedures. Toxic plants such as birthwort, hemlock, and arum are no longer used [Niedenthal 2020].

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Document metadata

Title: Odo Magdunensis and the *Macer floridus*

Author: Tobias Niedenthal (Forscherguppe Klostermedizin, Würzburg) — ORCID: [0000-0001-5975-1210](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5975-1210)

Version: 1.1 (2 Jan 2026)

Status: Public release

Suggested citation: Niedenthal T. Odo Magdunensis and the *Macer floridus*. Version 1.1; 2 Jan 2026. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17410453](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17410453)

Funding: none

Competing interests: none

Correspondence: Tobias Niedenthal

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Zenodo metadata (EN/DE)

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DE Kurzaabstract: Odo Magdunensis' *De viribus herbarum* (in der Überlieferung als *Macer floridus*) ist ein lateinisches hexametrisches Lehrgedicht über Arzneipflanzen, das im Mittelalter zu einem Standardbezugspunkt der Materia medica wurde. Das Werk bündelt spätantike Autoritäten, insbesondere Dioskurides, Plinius und Galen, und nimmt in erweiterter Form die Gradlehre aus Constantinus Africanus (*Liber graduum*) auf. Die Überlieferung ist durch Offenheit für Umstellungen und Zuwachs gekennzeichnet, darunter die *Spuria Macri* und die deutsche Vulgatafassung (um 1220). Eine moderne kritische Edition des lateinischen Textes steht weiterhin aus.

Related identifiers (DOI): [10.5281/zenodo.17410453](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17410453)

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